

Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray from a Distance

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I am extremely thankful to the Council of the Indian Chemical Society for the honour they have done to me in asking me to deliver the Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray Memorial lecture for the year 1967. Any association with a great figure like Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray is an honour. I consider it to be a great honour to be called upon to speak on him as he happens to be one of the great sons of India who could become a legend in his life time. I happened to be a student of the Patna College and for a few months of the Science College. (Humanities and the Science Sections of the Patna College were separated in 1927. Patna College became the Arts College and the Science teaching went over to the Science College). I did not have the good fortune to come in contact with Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray. What I learnt of him from my teachers and newspapers and what I heard of him from Prof. Nil Ratan Dhar when he came to lecture in the Patna University in early twenties, was very inspiring. I first saw Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray in the company of Prof. F.G. Donnan in the University College, London some time between 1927 and 1929. Hence nothing which I am speaking today is the result of direct contact or direct knowledge. My knowledge about Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray is derived from what I heard about him as a student and as a teacher and what Prof. Priyada Ranjan Ray has written about him in the Biographical Memoirs of the National Institute of Sciences of India, from Presidency College Calcutta, Centenary Volume, 1955 and from 100 years of the University of Calcutta 1857 to 1956.

Nineteenth Century may be called the golden age of Bengal. This century produced a number of great men, in various walks of life. This was partly the result of Bengal coming in contact with the life and thought of the West, which was different from the life and thought of India. It was partly the result of quick and timely response of the Bengalees to changed conditions. Whenever there is peace and order in a country, and new ideas clash with old ideas, we get renaissance. New ideas are born, old and worn out ideas are modified or discarded and the tussle which goes on between old and new ideas and ideals sharpens the intellect of able and thinking young men and gives them ideal and zeal to change things for the better. India got peace after the British conquest of India. There was clash of ideas and ideals. No wonder that Bengal which was the most important scene of this clash produced giant religious reformers, like Raja Ram Mohan Roy, great religious teachers, like Parmhans Ram Krishna and Swami Vivekanand, great lawyers like Rash Bihari Ghosh and Tarak Nath Palit, great politicians, like Surendra Nath Banerjee, Chittaranjan Das,

Twentieth Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray memorial lecture delivered at Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics, Calcutta on August, 2, 1967.

Bepin Chandra Pal, great litterateurs, like Michael Madhusudan, Bankim Chandra Chatterji and Rabindra Nath Tagore, great educationists, like Iswar Chandra Vidyasagar and Ashutosh Mukerjee and great scientists like Prafulla Chandra Ray and Jagdish Chandra Bose. I have only given illustrations. I have not even made an attempt to include all the great men of the period. There must have been large number of omissions. I assure you that no omission is deliberate. I hope I will be excused for the omissions.

Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray was born on August 2, 1861. His father Shri Harish Chandra Ray was a landed proprietor of Jessore (subsequently Khulna) district. Now Khulna forms a part of Pakistan, Harish Chandra Ray was fortunate in having come in close contact with eminent intellectuals of his time, including Iswar Chandra Vidyasagar. Harish Chandra Ray was proficient in English and Persian. He was also fairly acquainted with Arabic and Sanskrit. He did not represent the orthodox 'no changer' section of the Society. Rather he was liberal in his views. Prafulla Chandra Ray must have imbibed liberalism from his father at an early age. The scholarly atmosphere of his father's home also must have influenced his life.

Acharya Prafulla Chandra's elementary education did not progress well. He was admitted in the village school. His childhood coincided with period when Bengalees in order to give better education to their children or to have gainful employment were shifting to Calcutta from their villages. Harish Chandra Ray also moved to Calcutta from Jessore. Young Prafulla Chandra joined Hare School, but he could not continue there for long. He got dysentery and had to discontinue going to school. His not going to school did not result in 'no study' as it happens in a large number of cases. He utilised his time in studying English and Bengali literature and history of a number of countries. He then joined Albert School started by Keshab Chandra Sen. Keshab Chandra Sen was one of the pioneer social reformers of Bengal. He is to a large extent responsible for making Brahma Samaj popular in Bengal. Keshab Chandra Sen did not want to confine himself to public speeches. Keshab Chandra Sen was keen on having a school where the teachers would have high ideals and be keen on social reforms. That explains the foundation of Albert School. When young Prafulla Chandra recovered from dysentery and was able to join a school, his father preferred Albert School to any other school. Young Prafulla Chandra passed his Entrance Examination from the Albert School. The Entrance Examination changed to Matriculation and has now become the School Final Examination.

Metropolitan Institution managed by Iswar Chandra Vidyasagar was affiliated by the Calcutta University to the First Arts standard in 1872 and became a first grade college in 1879. Metropolitan Institution was famous in its own way. It had a number of persons on its staff who were social reformers and were well known political leaders of their time. Surendra Nath Banerjee, the idol of India used to teach English literature in the Metropolitan Institution. Young Prafulla Chandra passed his Entrance examination in 1878 and joined the Metropolitan Institution. The reason for going to

this Institute must have been the same which had been to join the Albert School. The first Indian Vice Chancellor of the Calcutta University Shri Gooroodas Banerjee described Metropolitan Institution in 1892 as the "first affiliated private college which has served as a model for many others that have since come into existence." Metropolitan Institution is now known as Vidyasagar College. Teachers of the Metropolitan Institution and specially Surendra Nath Banerjee must have been responsible for creating a love for the country in young Prafulla Chandra, love which remained for his whole life and which grew stronger with age. Young Prafulla Chandra Ray though very good in studies of humanities was keen on reading science. He had to read science for his F.A. course. Metropolitan Institution had no arrangement for teaching science. For reading science portion of his F.A. course he had to go to Presidency College. Presidency College had a famous man as Professor of Chemistry at that time, I mean Sir Alexander Pedlar. He was a gifted teacher. He used to show a large number of experiments in his class. He was also an excellent research worker. He was the first Fellow of Royal Society from the Presidency College, others being Sir J. C. Bose and Professor P. C. Mahalanobis. Young Prafulla Chandra Ray must have been very much influenced and inspired by Sir Alexander. To what extent Sir Alexander was responsible for young Prafulla Chandra Ray, choosing Chemistry as his career is difficult to say. After passing his F. A. examination Prafulla Chandra joined B. A. 'B' course of the Calcutta University. In those days 'B' course was Science course and 'A' course was the humanity course. While still a student of the B. A. classes he competed for the Gilchrist Prize for which knowledge of four different languages was essential. He was able to get the prize. Very few students who have so good a taste in languages as to get Gilchrist prize go in for scientific studies. Young Prafulla Chandra, however, decided to use his prize for studying science at Edinburgh. He took Chemistry at Edinburgh in 1882. He was a student of Prof. Tait and Professor Crum Brown. James Walker who was his class mate succeeded Prof. Crum Brown. The present generation still remembers Crum Brown for his rule of substitution of the various hydrogen atoms in benzene ring. James Walker who was a well known author when I was a student of the Hons. Class at Patna seems to have been forgotten. Acharya Prafulla Chandra took his Bachelor's degree from Edinburgh in 1885. He could not be satisfied with taking a degree and joining service as early as possible. He joined research and took his D.Sc. degree in 1888, from the Edinburgh University. He was admitted to this degree on the basis of his work on Conjugated Sulphates of the Copper Magnesium Group : A study of Isomorphous Mixture and Molecular combination. He was able to secure Hope Prize of the University which enabled him to work for a year more at Edinburgh. It was during this period that he was elected Vice President of the Chemical Society of the University. It should not be forgotten that in the nineteenth century Indians were considered by Europeans to be intellectually inferior. Any achievement by an Indian helped to remove this feeling and added to the stature and glory of the country. Thus even as a young man Prafulla Chandra Ray raised the stature of the country by getting a D.Sc. degree.

In 1888 after getting a D. Sc. degree, any Indian expected to be well provided. In these days we had Indian Educational Service to which mostly Englishmen were appointed, but Indians of rare distinction were also appointed to the Indian Educational Service even in the nineteenth century. Prafulla Chandra had rubbed the British Government on the wrong side. While a student at Edinburgh in the Bachelor's classes he wrote an article on "India Before and After the Mutiny". In this article Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray had not spared the British Government from criticism. While India was a part of British Empire, Secretary of States for India was the appointing authority in case of Indian Educational Service. When the then Dr. P. C. Ray approached the Secretary of State for India, he was not favoured with an appointment in the Indian Educational Service. Acharya Prafulla Chandra came back to India in 1888. He met his teacher Sir Alexander. He also met the Director of Public Instructions. He had an interview with the Lieutenant Governor of Bengal. He was then appointed as Assistant Professor of Chemistry in Bengal Educational Service and joined Presidency College in July, 1889. In 1888-89 D. Sc. degree was a much greater thing than today and an average person, if his merit was not recognised, would have felt so much frustrated that he would not have been able to do anything after D. Sc. and would have given up research. Acharya Prafulla Chandra was, however, made of a different stuff. The greater the difficulties the greater was the determination to overcome them. Acharya Prafulla Chandra cared very little for rewards. He was a real *Karma-Yogi* who believed that he had the right to perform his duties only and he had no worry about rewards. As a matter of fact he did not care for rewards. If they came they were welcome. If they did not, it did not matter. On joining the Presidency College he threw himself headlong in his work as a teacher and as a research worker.

He was an excellent teacher. He demonstrated his lectures with suitable experiments. He took individual interests in his students. The more devoted a student was in his class, the more he was loved by Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray. The late Dr. Rajendra Prasad told me, how much Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray liked him. Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray wanted young Rajendra Prasad to take Chemistry, but Rajendra Prasad had greater bent for humanities and took up humanities. It shows that Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray used to take great care of even First Arts students. He also made his teaching interesting by relating several anecdotes connected with various discoveries.

Proper demonstration of experiments at lower stage of teaching, drawing of conclusions from them, so as to develop the rational thinking of students, close contacts with the students so that they can resolve their difficulties, are necessary. If the teacher is a man of character, close contact also leads to development of character of students and some of the students turn out to be idealists like their teacher. On account of enormous increase in the number of students after 1937, the facilities of the laboratories have become much poorer. Many of the colleges have so many classes in the same room that there is hardly any scope for arranging a good number of experiments.

In some cases teaching load also is heavy. Prices of chemical and apparatus have gone up very high. The grant except perhaps in the case of Universities financed by the Government of India have not kept pace with the increase in prices. The number and prices have created a very difficult situation. Maintenance of standard has become very difficult. Quoting simply that U. S. A., U. S. S. R., or U. K. has so many Science graduates per 1000 of population has no meaning if we cannot provide adequate facilities for the maintenance of standards. A student who does not learn the importance of accuracy will not care for accuracy as a teacher or as an industrial worker. Lowering of the standard will mean the slowing of the progress of the country. We should not forget that we are living in a competitive world. If we are inefficient we will be eliminated. We cannot be inefficient and at the same time aspire for the standard of living of the West. Aspiration for good food, good housing, cultural activities is legitimate, but one has to work for them whatever be the walk of the life. In 1929 when I came back from England I did not find much difference in standard of B. Sc. (Special) London. Tripos Part II of Cambridge and similar degrees of other Universities in England and the M.Sc. of Indian Universities except that in England training as a Chemist for working in industries was always kept in mind. For instance 100% analysis of two or more ores, analysis of metals by electro deposition was done by all students for the Hons. course. Even now English Universities retain the bias. In 1964 I found that every student in Chemistry at London who had gone in for the Special Course was required to work in Infra Red Spectroscopy as Infra Red Spectroscopy is being extensively used in industries. I do not mind one or two sophisticated instrument not being used because they do not form the backbone of training. What forms the backbone is setting up of standard experiments with full understanding and getting correct result from them. When I find that this is being neglected in many Universities even at the M.Sc. stage, I feel very unhappy.

Acharya Prafulla Chandra was not an ordinary individual. He was an institution in himself. His life had many bright facets. One was that he was an excellent and inspiring teacher. The second bright facet of his life was research. As pointed out earlier he had little facilities for research when he joined Presidency College. His first paper appeared in 1894 five years after he joined Presidency College. It was not on any specific problem of Inorganic, Organic or Physical Chemistry, but it was on 'Determination of Adulteration in Food Stuffs. It was published in the Journal of Asiatic Society of Bengal. His important publications really began with Mercurous Nitrite in 1896. He obtained it in yellow crystals, by the action on mercury of dilute nitric acid containing nitrous acid. This was followed by a large number of papers on nitrite and hyponitrites, prepared by diverse methods. For instance, he prepared mercuric hyponitrite by the action of potassium cyanide on mercuric nitrate. He prepared the nitrites of the Alkali and alkaline earths in a pure state. He studied the action of heat on them. He observed that magnesium nitrite was less stable than nitrites of Ca, Sr or Ba and its stability was more like that of nitrites of the sub-group 'B' of the Periodic

Table. He prepared a number of double nitrites of Mercury II with barium, calcium and lithium and found the stability of the double nitrites of mercury decreased with the increasing atomic weight of the other metal. He next extended his researches to the preparation of compounds consisting of Mercuric Nitrite and alkyl amines and aryl amines. These had the composition $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_2)_2 \text{RNH}_2$. When Ethylenediamine was used the compound formed was $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_2)_2 \text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2$. He next prepared a number of compounds such as methyl ammonium nitrite and other alkyl ammonium nitrites in a pure state. The method was neat. He used silver nitrite and alkyl ammonium chloride in solution for the preparation of the above. He studied the decomposition and sublimation of ammonium nitrite. Later on with N.R. Dhar he succeeded in vapourising ammonium nitrite without any decomposition or dissociation. This was an outstanding experiment. The ammonium nitrite in solution starts decomposing very rapidly when the temperature is raised. Few expected that ammonium nitrite could be converted into vapour even without any dissociation. Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray did not confine himself to Inorganic Chemistry. He went to Physical Chemistry also when necessary. Along with J. C. Ghosh he measured the dissociation constant of nitrous acid. Nitrous acid was concentrated by freezing it, a method extensively used when high temperature decomposes the compound in solution. Dissociation constant measurements showed nitrous acid to be a weak acid. Its velocity of decomposition was also studied by them. The most glorious days of Acharya Ray was spent in Presidency College. He published about forty papers by himself and an equal number with his pupils. This was between 1895 and 1916, a period of 21 years. With modern facilities it may not appear to be a great feat, but for the facilities available at that time it was a tremendous feat.

Ashutosh Mukherji became the Vice-Chancellor of the Calcutta University in 1906. He was not satisfied with the mere examining nature of the Calcutta University. He wanted the University to take up teaching and research, which was possible under the amended act of 1904. He strongly felt that without a teaching University, research could not get the impetus it deserved. He did not like that India should exist on borrowed knowledge for all times. He felt that Indians should be given a chance to make their share of contribution to the advancement of Science. Ashutosh Mukherji's idea about a University can be judged from the following extract from his first convocation address of the Calcutta University :

“It is not the number but the quality of students, it is not the quantum of knowledge but the character of the training received that determines the position of the University. It is paramount duty of the University to discover and develop unusual talent. No University is worthy of its reputation which does not enrol among its professors, men best fitted to advance the bounds of knowledge. No University can rightly be regarded as fulfilling the purpose of its existence, unless it affords to the best of its students, adequate encouragement to carry on research and unless it enables intellectual power whenever detected to exercise its highest functions.”

Soon after the assumption of office as Vice-Chancellor Ashutosh Mukherji struggled hard to establish Post Graduate teaching and to provide facilities for research. The University had no funds to start the Departments of Science and Technology. In 1912 Tarak Nath Palit, an eminent member of the English Bar of Calcutta, popularly known as Barrister-at-law, made over to the University of Calcutta assets worth seven lakhs of rupees, four and half lakhs in cash and two and half lakhs in property. The conditions of his endowment were that the University should found two professorships—one in Chemistry and the other in Physics, from out of the income of the endowment and in case the income proved insufficient for the maintenance of the two chairs, the University should make such recurring grant or contribution as would supplement the deficiency. The object of the founder in his own word was “the promotion and diffusion of scientific and technical education and the cultivation and advance of science, pure and applied, amongst his countrymen by and through indigenous agency. Such chairs shall always be filled by Indians (persons born of Indian parents as contradistinguished from persons who are called statutory natives of India) to be nominated by a Governing body.”

The endowment led to the foundation of a Chair in Chemistry and a Chair in Physics. Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray after his retirement from Presidency College in 1916 was appointed to the Chair in Chemistry as Palit Professor of Chemistry. As Palit Professor he took up the study of compounds of metallic elements with organic sulphur derivatives particularly the mercaptans and sulphides. A full account of these has been given in the Lecture by Prof. J. N. Ray in 1961. A number of double sulphates of triethyl and trimethyl sulphonium bases with metals of copper, magnesium etc. having the general composition $2\text{MSO}_4(\text{R}_2\text{S})_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where $\text{M} = \text{Fe, Zn, Ni, Co or Cd}$, $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$, or C_2H_5 were prepared and studied. Similar double salts with phosphonium bases were also prepared and reported. Several compounds of some alkyl sulphides with silver nitrate were prepared and studied in detail. The reaction between hydrated ferric chloride and ethyl sulphide gave the compound $\text{HFeCl}_4(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. Its reaction with organic bases like pyridine, quinoline and *o*-toluidine were also investigated and reported. Varying valency of platinum gold and irridium also attracted his attention. For a number of years Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray and his students worked on this problem.

As a research worker he was good, but he was better in inspiring his students. He created permanent interest in Chemistry in the minds of many young men who came in contact with him. Among his research students who made a name for themselves are Panchanan Niyogi, Rasik Lal Dutta, Hemendra Kumar Sen, Nilratan Dhar, Jnan Chandra Ghosh, Jnanendra Nath Mukherji, Biman Bihar Dey, Priyada Ranjan Ray, P. C. Guha, P. K. Bose and Biresh Chandra Guha. They in their turn founded schools of research. The research in Chemistry which we see in India today has to an appreciable extent grown from the sapplings of the tree planted by

Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray. Indirectly he enthused many to join research, even in branches other than Chemistry.

The foundation of the Indian Chemical Society is to a large extent due to him. In fitness of things he became the first President of the Society. There were many Chemists in 1923 who felt that we would not be able to run a journal in India. They stood for sending their papers abroad. In 1923 when Indian Chemical Society was founded, its Journal appeared quarterly. With passage of time it became a monthly journal. Now though a large amount of researches is published outside the Journal in India and abroad, there is no dearth of material for the journal. We are all thankful to the foresight of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray in founding the Society.

Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray was a great philanthropist. He was frugal in his habits. He had no pomp and show. He had a very simple and inexpensive life. Whatever he saved by simple living was spent in doing good to others. I have no personal knowledge but I have been told that he helped his students who were in financial need. Even persons who were not his students got help from him. When he completed his sixtieth year in 1921 he offered to resign Palit Professorship. He was persuaded to stay on as a Professor. He decided to make a gift of the salary he received from the Calcutta University. His salary from 1921 to 1936 was allowed to accumulate and the accumulated sum came to Rs. 1,80,000/- in 1936. This is perhaps the largest gift a teacher of the Calcutta University has made. This money has been spent by the University on the development of the Department of Chemistry and for the creation of two research fellowship. Acharya Ray also made a gift of Rs. 10,000/- for an annual prize in Chemistry named after the great alchemist of India, Nagarjuna. At the time of his retirement in 1936 he made another endowment of Rs. 10,000/- for a research prize in Zoology and Botany named after Sir Ashutosh Mookherji.

From his early years Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray realised the importance of industries. He fully realised that science gave rise to industries and industries in their turn helped the development of science. Unless science and industries acted and reacted a country could not progress. When he came back from United Kingdom in 1888 there was hardly any chemical industry in the country. In 1894 he started preparing Pharmaceutical products on a small scale in his own house. He later on persuaded some friends and helpmates to join him and started Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works Ltd. which developed in course of time and is now one of the important Chemical and Pharmaceutical concerns of the country. He always advised youngmen to go in for trade and industries. There is no doubt that his words must have carried weight and a number of youngmen must have gone in for industries. I am not in a position to name important persons who were influenced by him and went to industries.

Another shining facet of the life of Acharya Ray was his zeal for social reforms. He knew the immobility created by the caste system. He was also aware of the injustice involved in the perpetration of caste system. He believed in the equality of human beings. He accepted the equality and not inequality as basis of society.

He did not accept the ideal that the lower castes were inferior and the whole monopoly of wisdom was with the upper castes. He did not agree, that the division of labour as envisaged in the caste system, should continue. He did not see the logic in castes not intermarrying. He did not like the exploitation which exists in the name of caste system. He seldom missed an opportunity of speaking against the caste system. If he was opposed to the existence of caste system he was violently opposed to the existence of untouchability in the Hindu Society. He considered it to be inhuman, barbarous and unjustifiable on any ground. He used to ridicule the idea that things could change by touching the vessels and things could become polluted by touch. The more he realised the harm, pollution by touch was doing to the Hindu Society, the more he preached against it. Years before Mahatma Gandhi started his movement against untouchability, Acharya Prafulla Ray presided over the Indian National Social Conference at Calcutta. That was in 1917. In his presidential speech he made an impassioned appeal for the removal of untouchability from the Hindu Society.

He was a patriot right from his childhood. His studies in the Albert School and Metropolitan Institute fortified his patriotism. He felt that India was great and should be great once again. Sir William Jones and his followers who studied Sanskrit literature, Vedas, etc. found the great store house of Philosophy in India. They felt that Hinduism was not to be judged by the existing society but by its philosophy and literature. A large number of persons felt that India had only a philosophical past, and she had no great scientific achievement to her credit in the past. The patriot in Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray could not have felt happy with this idea. He was a scientist. He could not conjure up stories of her past scientific achievements. He decided to examine the past and see if India had scientific achievements in past. By this investigation he found that India had a great past so far as Chemistry was concerned. His great book—History of Hindu Chemistry—records the achievement of India in the field of Chemistry in the olden days. Though he did not participate actively in any political movement for the freedom of the country, his personal sympathy was always there. He whole-heartedly supported the constructive programme of the Congress as formulated by Mahatma Gandhi. Very often people think that only those who agitate are patriots. They forget that all those who help in making a nation honest, hard-working and efficient are also patriots and sometimes of a superior kind.

Seen from any angle Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray was a great man. Honours even if he did not care for them were bound to come to him. The British Government though they did not like him, must have considered it unfair not to confer honour on him. He became C.I.E. (Companion of the Indian Empire) in 1912. The British Government honoured him with a Knighthood in 1919. When I became a student of the Patna University in 1922 people used to call him as Sir P. C. or Sir P. C. Ray. The greatest honour conferred on him was the title of Acharya which means a preceptor—not a mere Professor who professes a subject but

a real teacher who has sound knowledge and has high character, from whom, people not only learn the subject he professes, but also draw inspiration for a healthy and useful life.

I conclude this lecture with the full belief that his life would serve as an inspiration to us indirectly in the same manner in which it inspired students who same in direct contact with him.